

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Tracking changes in Filipino's search trend between dentures and implants from 2021-22: A descriptive study

Corenne Adriane Bantigue^{ID}, Dianne Quisido^{ID},
Rebekah Levnai Montes^{ID}, Mary Wilrose Torrano^{ID},
Rachelle Joy Abregoso^{ID}, Khloweje Ken Golindang^{ID}

ABSTRACT

Background: A study in 2019 revealed that 28% of the total older Filipino population is completely edentulous and it is increasing significantly throughout the years. **Methods:** This study compared the trends of Filipino web searchers regarding dentures and Implants from August 2021 to July 2022 using “dentures” (D) and “implants” (I) as search terms, the Philippines as location, health as category, and Web search as database. **Results:** The outcome showed a decreasing trend in searches for Implants and an increasing interest in denture web searches from August 2021 - July 2022. Multiple comparisons of monthly results showed that searches for D were significantly higher than I by 25-100%. In fact, on July 31- August 6, 2022 the difference in search trend is 100%. Searches from Caraga, Bicol, and Ilocos Region compared to other regions in the Philippines were significantly higher. **Discussion:** The search for Implants is relatively low compared to Dentures from 2021-2022 in the Philippines. **Conclusions:** This study can be used as another basis that supports the need for improvement of the dental care system in the Philippines.

Keywords implants, dentures, data mining, health-seeking behavior, dental care, Philippines

Corresponding author

Bantigue, Corenne Adriane R.,
coru.bantigue.swu@phinmaed.com, 0908-683-7052

1 | Introduction

Tooth loss, whether partial or complete, is a major public health concern worldwide due to its high prevalence and associated disability.

Although it's not fatal, edentulism has a great impact on facial appearance, nutrition, and the ability to eat, speak, and socialize. Compared to high-income countries, the rate of edentulism is rising in low- and middle-income (LMIC). Due to this, the Philippines, one of the low- and middle-income nations (LMICs), has a

high rate of edentulism among its people.¹

Untreated caries and periodontal diseases are the primary causes of tooth loss, eventually leading to complete edentulism.² Despite the development of restorative and preventative dentistry, edentulism continues to be a difficult issue for medical professionals around the globe. It is referred to as the "ultimate marker of disease load for oral health."³

Edentulism is linked to a variety of factors including age. This is a significant contributing component to the epidemiology of edentulism and it is evident that the elder age group is the most affected. Four in 10 elderly Filipinos without any natural teeth still experience the negative effects of not having any teeth at all, natural or artificial.² Lifestyle choices such as smoking, drinking, and eating carbohydrate-rich foods, economic conditions, education, oral health knowledge and beliefs, and attitudes toward dental care can all be attributed to a lack of or limited access to dental care. For instance, tooth extraction is frequently the sole treatment option for dental issues in settings with low resources; this practice results in early tooth loss.³ A large proportion of Filipino adults had unmet oral health needs, and the main barrier to seeking care at a dental office was a lack of adequate finances.⁴

Tooth loss significantly reduces one's quality of life. It impairs speech, aesthetics, and mastication, as well as social functioning. It also harms the patient's mental health. The loss of an important part of the body and an impaired self-image may cause depression and low self-esteem. This increases the demand for prosthetic teeth to replace missing teeth.⁵

Although dental implants are increasingly used to support dental prostheses because they are more functional and aesthetically similar to natural teeth, traditional removable dentures are still used in many cases due to financial and/or medical considerations, despite disadvantages such as promoting more movement during function and requiring more maintenance. Patients' desire to replace missing teeth is influenced by a variety of factors, including the availability of dental services and the patients' educational, financial, and social status.⁵

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the preference of Filipinos between dentures and implants based on their intervener search trends. Moreover, the objective of the study includes unraveling the search pattern of Dentures and Dental implants among Filipinos in the year 2021-2022.

Figure 1. Temporal difference of search interests for implants and dentures from August 1, 2021 to July 31, 2022 in the Philippines.

2| Results

2.1. Temporal Difference

Majority of the Filipinos in the year 2021 searched highest for Implants in October – November 2021 at an average of 61.25% while the lowest was only at an average of 43.4% November – December 2021. On the other hand, the highest search average for Dentures was at 53.8% while the lowest was at an average of 51.8%. (Figure 1)

In 2022 Filipinos interest in Implant grew over to an average of 63.4% in February 2022, while the lowest average was only at 50% in June. The search trend in Dentures also grew over to an average of 70% in August

while the lowest average was only at 20.3% in January 2022. (Figure 1).

Majority of the Filipinos in the year 2021 searched highest for Dentures in November 28 – December 4, 2021 at 87%, while the highest for Implants was only at 71% last November 7 - 13, 2021.

In 2022 Filipinos interest for Dentures grew over to a 100% in July 31 – August 6, 2022, while the highest for implant was at 77% last May 1 – 7, 2022. (Figure 1)

2.2. Geographical Discrepancy

Figure 2. Compared breakdown by subregions of denture and implants.

In terms for the highest searches for Dentures the first ranked subregion (62%) Caraga followed by Bicol (59%), Ilocos Region (58%), Central Luzon (57%) and Eastern Visayas (57%). (Figure 2)

On the other hand, in terms for the highest searches for Implants the first ranked subregion (58%) Northern Mindanao followed by MIMAROPA (57%), Region XII (54%), Zamboanga Peninsula (53%) and Davao Region (53%) (Figure 2)

3| Discussion

Based on the results of this study, it may be assumed that the majority of Filipinos opted for dentures over implants given the low devaluation of implants, which occurs between August 15, 2021, and August 15 of 2022. Filipinos' interest in denture restoration is evident from the sharp increase in denture-related web searches. Nine million individuals in the Philippines use dentures in urban

settings, making it the country with the highest percentage of denture users in Asia, according to a study by an international pharmaceutical company. The increasing growth can be linked to the limited access that Filipinos have to oral hygiene, the costly expense of dental care, the lack of awareness of oral personal hygiene in particular, and its effects on self-confidence. The graph demonstrates that over the period of a year, the second wave continuously grew at the peak of the pandemic. There have been 2 significant stages of tooth replacement in the nation, namely dentures and implants. Roland, J (2021), states in his study that the ideal treatment plan for you will depend on your budget, personal preferences, and the condition of one's jawbone and remaining teeth. In the end, dentures and implants equally help you chew food, support facial muscles, enhance communication and speech, boost your confidence and lessen self-consciousness by enabling you to smile. Compared to dentures, which may occasionally need adjustments or replacement throughout time, implants may last 20 years or longer. In order to support the posts on implants, a considerable amount of jawbone material is expected. In contrast to implants, dentures can be fitted no matter how much bone already exists. Dentures require more daily attention when it comes to maintenance than

dental implants do, but apart from that, they require similar dental hygiene that is required by natural teeth, such as brushing and flossing at least twice a day and a number of required appointments. Furthermore, as stated by Liaw K, (2015) dental implants are typically safe and effective replacements for missing teeth with a low risk of complications like infectious disease and mechanical problems. In comparison, dentures normally come with complications like gum ulceration and dentures that don't stay in place.

As stated in a study of an international pharmaceutical company, there are more Filipinos than people from other Asian countries who prefer dentures, making us one of the highest denture users in the region. Nine million individuals wear dentures in the Philippines' urban areas alone, with 61 percent of them female and 39 percent of them male, according to a study entitled "Oral Care U&A Market Understanding Study Middle East and Asia." According to the study, Metro Manila is the place of residence for 80% of individuals who wear dentures, followed by Metro Cebu at 9% and Metro Davao at 6%. Isa Marfori reported that 56% of wearers claimed irresponsible oral hygiene as their primary reasoning, followed by 9% accident-related tooth loss and 12% illness-related tooth loss. Considering graph figure 1, it is safe to assume that

Filipinos prefer dentures over implants. According to Aubert E, one of the pros of dentures is that they are less expensive than implants, thus perhaps the decision may be attributed to this. Drilling into the bone is not necessary for dentures, therefore the operation is also non-invasive. Contrarily, a 2018 Dental Tourism article titled "Having Dental Implants in the Philippines" claims that dental implants are the greatest long-term option for replacing missing teeth. But most people cannot afford dental implants, particularly if they reside in nations where even the expense of basic dental treatment is unaffordable. The average cost of dental implants in Australia is AUD \$ 3,800, but only AUD \$ 1,700 in the Philippines, according to an article titled The Ultimate Guide to Dental Implants in the Philippines (2020). Despite dental implants being pricey, as can be seen from the graph, there are still some people who choose these. We cannot disclose if the majority of these are Filipinos. According to an article in Dental Travel Services 2022 titled "Australians Traveling to the Philippines for Dental Implants," the government's cooperation and engagement with the case comes first, which is one reason dental care in the Philippines is so excellent when it comes to quality and reasonably priced. The Philippines set out to expressly establish the first-world system in order for dental offices to advance and

take the lead in the industry. As usual, price is determined by demand and supply. As a consequence, prices have risen. Dentists are more abundant in the Philippines than elsewhere, and as a result, costs are reduced. According to the same article, Australians, and Kiwis who live close by coming to the Philippines to replace their missing teeth because our dental costs are lower than those in their country while still offering high-quality care and the opportunity to travel.

Most Common Dental Problems in the Philippines revealed that individuals typically ignore dental health issues and only pay attention to them when something doesn't feel right. Both adults and teenagers may experience dental problems, and toothaches are among the illnesses that people complain about the most. Poor oral hygiene and poor dental treatment are to blame for this. It is crucial that we practice appropriate personal hygiene, especially when it comes to our teeth, as this could cause more serious health issues. The article "Dental Health What You Can Do About Missing Teeth" provides a list of the causes of tooth loss, including inherited diseases, gum disease, injuries, cavities, and tooth decay. It is necessary to have them replaced because they can disrupt chewing habits, lead to bone loss, and have an unpleasant effect on self-esteem. The prosthodontist can educate you in

deciding the best way to replace your missing tooth. Dentures or dental implants are two options for replacement. According to Technavio (2016), restorative dentistry is the new, rapidly gaining popularity trend in the dental profession. One of the most common restorative dentistry procedures today is dental prosthetics that can replace missing teeth or missing teeth. Additionally, he cited the top 5 pros of dental prosthetics, including less bone loss, support for partial dentures, efficient oral rehabilitation and maintenance, improved aesthetics, and improved quality of life. Therefore, it is crucial to increase access to dental care, especially for extremely underprivileged people. In areas where access to care and costs are major concerns, the need for high-quality dental care services has historically been overlooked, according to Dentistry for Every Village Foundation, Inc. access to care issues are particularly challenging to handle in underdeveloped and financially struggling towns. Therefore, the extent of executing the services drastically increases if the local government is overly preoccupied with other issues. Due to a number of factors, such as the state of the economy and a lack of facilities to provide the necessary level of care, oral health is often neglected, sometimes for years. The necessity for the government to support everyone

in living a happy life should therefore be prioritized. They should have a program, particularly a dental mission.

It should be emphasized that there are limitations to this study. According to this survey, Filipinos can only afford dentures rather than implants, and more of us prefer them than those from other Asian nations, making us the country with the highest denture usage in the region. Metro Manila, Metro Cebu, and Metro Davao are some areas where Filipinos can be found wearing dentures. Because they are more economical than implants, dentures are the most searched-for item on Google Trends, which suggests that many people only consider wearing them due to budgetary constraints.

4 | Methods

4.1. Design

This study analyzed search trends using Google Trends by collecting internet search data and analyzing dentures and implants.

(<https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?cat=45&date=2021-08-01%202022-08-31&geo=PH&q=implants,dentures>).

4.2. Search Parameters

Google Trends is filled with information regarding search trends using the search terms “denture” and “implants”, the Philippines as location, 2021-2022 as years of interest, health

as category, and web search as database, Specifically the time period used for 2021 was August 1 to July of 2022.

4.3. Data acquisition

Google Trends data is collected in order to obtain accurate data on search trends. Because Google Trends is populated with data that appears in plain text, the details collected are reorganized and imported into tables and charts for easy viewing of results.

4.4. Statistical analysis

The survey provided a detailed description of the data collected. However, the survey is limited to the period from August 2021 until July 2022.

5 | Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, more people looked for dentures than implants. Dentures were the most frequently sought item by Filipinos in 2021 (87%), followed by implants (71%). This demonstrates that dentures are of greater interest to the majority of Filipinos. The percentage of Filipinos who search for dentures rather than implants is larger each month. Caraga, Bicol, the Ilocos Region, Central Luzon, and the Eastern Visayas are some of the regions that have received the most research on dentures. Similar to Northern Manila,

MIMAROPA, Region XII, Zamboanga Peninsula, and Davao Region, these areas also performed well in implant search trends, indicating that these areas are more interested in implants. Dentures continued to be of more interest than implants in 2021–2022, despite the fact that interest in this topic is still growing. These results can be used to evaluate the healthcare system in the Philippines as to why more people opt for dentures even when implants offer a better prognosis. This can also mean that people over the years prefer less expensive options for their dental needs. This may also have a correlation to our economic status. This study is limited to the search trends of dentures and implants from 2021-2022 and the most searched among the two.

This study will be useful to Filipinos who wish to know which dental procedure—implants or dentures—is more frequently searched for as well as to future researchers.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, B.C., Q.D.; Original Draft Presentation, B.C.; Validation, T.M., Q.D., Title, B.C.; Abstract, B.C.; Editing, B.C., Q.D, T.M., G.K., A.R.; Introduction, Q.D.; Result, M.R.;

References

1. Tyrovolas S, Koyanagi A, Panagiotakos DB, et al.

Discussion, T.M.; Methods, G.K.; Conclusions, A.R., Citations, B.C., Q.D., T.M.;

Funding

This study received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thank the faculty members of the Southwestern University PHINMA School of Dentistry for their support in this study especially Dr. Junhel Dalanon for his mentoring us. Truly, we could not have done all these without your guide.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Population prevalence of edentulism and its association

- with depression and self-rated health. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6. doi:10.1038/SREP37083
2. Natividad JN, Cruz GT, Cruz CJP. Ageing and Health Philippines. <https://www.eria.org/uploads/media/Books/2019-Dec-Ageing-and-Health-Philippines/10-Ageing-and-Health-Philippines-Chapter-4-new.pdf>. Published online 2019.
 3. Al-Rafee MA. The epidemiology of edentulism and the associated factors: A literature Review. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2020;9(4):1841. doi:10.4103/JFMPC.JFMPC_1181_19
 4. Torresyap V, Hoover J, Torresyap M, Karunanayake C. Prosthodontic and Periodontal Status and Needs in a Selected Population of Urban Poor in the Philippines: A Pilot Study. doi:10.5005/jp-journals-10019-1093
 5. Fouda SM, Al-Harbi FA, Khan SQ, Virtanen JI, Raustia A. Missing teeth and prosthetic treatment in patients treated at College of Dentistry, University of Dammam. *Int J Dent.* 2017;2017. doi:10.1155/2017/7593540
 6. College of Dentistry, University of Dammam. *Int J Dent.* 2017;2017:7593540. doi:10.1155/2017/7593540
 7. Filipinos most bite-challenged among Asians. The Free Library. <https://www.thefreelibrary.com/Filipinos+most+bite-challenged+among+Asians-a0413783933>. Accessed September 7, 2022.
 8. Team Orange. Polident Embarks on Denture Care Awareness Campaign. <https://orangemagazine.ph/2015/polident-embarks-on-denture-care-awareness-campaign/>. Published May 25, 2015. Accessed August 19, 2022.
 9. Australians traveling to the Philippines for dental implants. Australians Traveling to Philippines for Implants - Dental Travel Services. <https://www.dentaltravelservices.com/australians-traveling-to-philippines-for-implants>. Accessed September 7, 2022.
 10. Gurarie M. Here's what you can do about missing teeth. Verywell Health. <https://www.verywellhealth.com/missing-teeth-5209485>. Published November 29, 2021. Accessed September 8, 2022.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

©The Author(s) 2022